

Dicing	Prep (min)	Machine (min)	Post (min)	Max n	Notes
Dicing Mask @(ADT)					
Put Optical Tape (blue) on pattern side to protect	5				Refer to PPT for detailed dicing instructions
Put dicing film for vacuum.	5	5	2		Film on opposite side of optical tape
Blade Mounting and mask Alignment	5	5			
ADT: 0 deg cut	10	15			6 cuts
ADT: 90 deg cut	10	10			6 cuts
Remove Blade					
Remove Optical Tape &					
Scribe wafer index SW corner back		7			Use diamond tip scribe. Write index #
Dry Etch @(SLR Plasma Etcher)					
PlasmaTherm //SLR Fluorine Etcher					Pressure: 5 [mTorr] CHF3 (30)/ O2 (15) [sccm] RF1:50[W] RF2:500 [W]
Insert 4" Carrier Wafer		5			
SLR: Flow -> O2/Ar Clean	5	10			
Insert grating					
SLR: CHF3/O2 Etch	5	6min25s			1 Desired depth: 578nm Etch Rate= 90nm/min or 1.5 nm/s
Unload Grating & load 4" carrier wafer					
SLR: Flow -> O2/Ar Clean		10			Cleaning. Minute per etch.
Chrome Etch (Cr-Etch)					
Remove Cr with Cr Etch	5	15			Might need to grab with forceps without touching the pattern & wash in solution to remove Chrome. Grab corner or sides.
Rinse with DI					
Rinse with Acetone and IPA					
Characterization AFM					
PeakForce Tapping Mode					FMV-A tips
AFM: Measure Step Depth	10	10			1 Increase to 3nN to 1nN if false engagement
AFM: Get Rq and Ra values of etched surface		10	5		
Packaging					
Wrap gratings individually in optical paper.		5			Label the packaging with marker and index number